

PROBE WG2 “Advanced ABL profiling” - Deliverable 2.1

Clouds and precipitation profiling

D2.1: Reports, white and review papers on key ABL parameters, their applications, and the end-user requirements.

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Project title (acronym)	Deliverable 2.1, Product: Clouds
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1 INTRODUCTION

This report aims at providing a synthesis of key ABL parameters for several applications and end-users with the corresponding existing algorithms. The information on end-users requirements will be filled later during the action after the finalization of the deliverable 1.2 that will be provided by working group 1 (knowledge exchange). For each group of products several references are provided so that the reader can get more details on specific products or accuracy evaluation.

Through all the documents the following acronyms are used:

- ALC: Automatic Lidar Ceilometer
- DL: Doppler Lidar
- MWR: MicroWave Radiometer
- DIAL: Differential Absorption Lidar
- DCR: Cloud Radar, Doppler Cloud Radar
- RL: Raman Lidar
- DeL: Depolarization Lidar
- BL: Backscatter lidar
- RWP: Radar Wind Profilers
- ABL: Atmospheric Boundary Layer

2 METHODS OVERVIEW

Instrument description for ABL profiling of clouds

One of the main instruments for cloud profiling within the ABL is the Cloud Radar (CR), operating either at 35 or 94 GHz. The use of ceilometers (ALC) is also extended within the cloud profiling community. The synergy of CL with ALC and MWRs is a powerful tool for the study of the vertical distribution of cloud properties and combined databases of the three instruments are usually used in the existing retrieval algorithms. Many stations within Europe are already continuously reporting within the CLOUDNET network (<https://cloudnet.fmi.fi/>) as part of ACTRIS, which combines CR, ALC and MWR for the detection, classification and retrieval of cloud properties.

For this section, these specific acronyms are used:

- DSD: Droplet Size Distribution
- CDNC: Cloud Droplet Number Concentration
- ACI: Aerosol-Cloud Interaction ⁵
- Reff: Effective Radius
- CF: Cloud Fraction
- LWC/IWC: Liquid/Ice Water Content
- OEM: Optimal Estimation Method

Available networks: ACTRIS/CLOUDNET, ARM

3 PRODUCT OVERVIEW

Products	Cloud detection / classification / CF	Liquid/Ice water content	Cloud optical depth	Microphysical properties	ACI ⁵
Instruments	- ALC - DL - DCR - DCR + ALC/DL	- ALC (with depolarisation) - DCR+ALC+MWR -RL	- DCR - RL - ALC+DCR -ALC+ sunphotometer	- DCR - ALC+DCR - ALC + DCR + MWR	- ALC+DCR - RL+DCR
Accuracy requirements (from WG1)					
Temporal resolution Requirement s (from WG1)	Optimal temporal resolution for CLADS to be effective is < 2s.				
Assumptions needed	Drizzle: Liquid clouds without ice phase, cloud base, cloud top CF: CF over time assumed to be projected area CF	- CR+MWR synergy: a DSD should be prescribed for LWC retrieval	Monomodal DSD for LWC	Monomodal DSD for LWC	Liquid water clouds only. Well-mixed conditions, CDNC and mono-modal gamma DSD constant with height
Existing algorithms	CLOUDNET ¹ (CR + ALC/DL, also provides target classification) Drizzle classification: CLADS ³ (DCR)	For LWC: -CLOUDNET ¹ -SYRSOC ² -IPT ⁸ for MWR + DCR -MWR+ DCR: OEM with model combination:	Liquid: SYRSOC ² Ice: DARDAR ¹⁰	Liquid: SYRSOC ² IPT ⁸ for MWR + DCR MWR+ DCR: OEM with model combination:	Sarna, 2015 ^{6,7}

		in development		in development	
		For IWC: CLOUDNET ¹ DARDAR ¹⁰		Ice: DARDAR ¹⁰	
		For drizzle water content: O'Connor ⁹		Drizzle: O'Connor ⁹ (operates within CLOUDNET)	
Applications	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Data Assimilation 2) Evaluation and verification in Numerical Weather Prediction 3) Climate and hydrological models 4) Satellite evaluation and Cal/Val. 				
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific community - NWP and other modelling communities - Space agencies 				
Readiness for operation	<p>CLOUDNET: Yes</p> <p>SYRSOC: No</p> <p>CLADS: In preparation</p> <p>IPT: Yes</p> <p>DARDAR: Yes</p> <p>OEM with model combination: No</p>				
Accuracy of existing products	Evaluation is difficult as these are the reference instruments. Drizzle classification requires evaluation	~20%	30-70%	~50% for CDNC 5-15% for r_{eff}^4 O'Connor provides LWF (drizzle liquid water flux) to within a factor	Further evaluation required

				of two	
Uncertainty estimates existing?	N	Y	Y	Y	N
Temporal resolution	< 30 seconds				
Timeliness	< 1 day (< 1 hour being testing)				
Data availability	24//7 For CLOUDNET, near-real-time (<1day)				
Data format	NetCDF for CLOUDNET products				

Note that there are many more algorithms for deriving cloud properties, some of which include additional instrumentation.

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